

TEXTUAL SURVEY OF FOUNDATIONAL VARIANCES OF PARLIAMENTARY PRIVILEGES IN INDIA AND SOUTH AFRICA

Pramod Gokul Kathane¹ and Shrinaag Arun Panchbhai^{1,2}

¹Department of Law, University of Mumbai and

²Institute of Forensic Sciences, Mumbai-32, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

Parliamentary privileges oblige as a constitutional shelter to the legislatures in India as well as South Africa, having a common source in the Westminster System of the United Kingdom. The said constitutional shelter comprises various immunities, such as to debate, to question, and to perform legislative duties free from external intrusions and forces. It seems that both democracies are ad idem in ensuring the democratic domain of constitutional shelter to their legislatures, but diverge on democratic inclusivity. It is said that the unique democratic inclusivity regime of the African constitution differs from that of republic India.

Further, the constitutional antiquity of India manifests hefty predominance to British historical practices and Common Law precedents while enacting privileges under Articles 105 and 194, including non-codification. Additionally, the judicial sacrosanct provided under Articles 122 and 212 at the ultimate resulted in compromising transparency and encroaching upon natural rights of the citizens. On the other hand, by enacting a three-tier mechanism in sections 58, 71, 117 and 161, the apartheid constitution of South Africa espouses a more organised and rights-focused method of balancing constitutional tenets as well as the basic rights of its citizens. Thus, South Africa has developed a vibrant constitutional model and judicial proactiveness, sharply distinct from India's tradition-based, uncoded balancing system.

KEYWORDS

Parliamentary privileges, constitutional rights, codification, non-accountability, inviolability, apartheid constitution, constitutional shelter, democratic inclusivity regime, bicameral Parliament and judicial proactiveness.

Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this paper is to extract a comprehensive and structured corollary about the position of parliamentary privileges that existed and developed in the republics of India and South Africa, including appraising the impact of codification on democratic accountability, transparency, and legislative independence. Further, to flash a light upon a core issue of developing contrast constitutional and legal architectures in Africa, to examine the correlation between the parliamentary privileges, constitutional rights and judicial review including detecting philosophical, structural, and functional differences between both Republics.

Simultaneously, it is also an aim of the study to comprehend why the Indian republic maintains an uncodified, convention-driven model, while South Africa follows a constitutionally codified and rights-oriented system. Thus, an objective is not merely to identify faintness in the Indian privilege mechanism, but to appraise practical challenges that crop up in India for want of codification and also to examine whether codification has strengthened institutional integrity in the Republic of South Africa and reduced conflicts between privileges and democratic rights compared to India

Research Methodology

The Author has adopted a qualitative, doctrinal, comparative and historical methodological framework to explore the parliamentary privileges subsisting in the republics of India and South Africa. This comprises a detailed examination of constitutional and statutory frameworks, including parliamentary rules and judicial interpretations. The doctrinal analysis would help to identify how the mechanism of privileges is operational in theory and the role of courts in shaping them in practice. The comparative methodology will help to highlight structural, functional, and philosophical differences between the two democratic mechanisms. By comparing two democratic jurisdictions having a common origin and distinct trajectories, the paper aims to reveal how constitutional choices shape modern democratic institutions. The historical method is used to trace an advancement of parliamentary privileges from British origin to their adaptation in colonial and post-colonial contexts. This will provide deeper insight into contemporary challenges. Lastly, researcher has used qualitative assessment methodology for examining instances of misuse, such as abuse of breach-of-privilege motions in India or constitutional conflicts in South Africa.

Review of Literature

For the study of the present paper, the researcher analyses secondary data, which includes academic texts, commentaries, legal journals, parliamentary reports, and scholarly critiques. This literature data on parliamentary privileges in India and South Africa reveals a long and complex trajectory shaped by constitutional history, British colonial influence, and evolving judicial interpretation. The researcher has examined the work of Erskine May, Enid Campbell, Ivor Jennings and Dicey, who maintain that privileges were core tools for securing legislative self-sufficiency and avoiding political vulnerability. The survey of literature of authors like M.P. Jain, V.D. Mahajan, D.D. Basu, H.M. Seervai, and A.G. Noorani depicted that in India, parliamentary privileges evolved out of a combination of colonial statutes and post-independence constitutional provisions, retaining powers equivalent to the British House of Commons, without a specific scope. To understand South Africa's privileges regime, the

researcher analyses the work of constitutional scholars such as Devenish, Woolman, N. Natlana and Choudhry and also examines literature relating to court precedents. The collective consideration literature demonstrates that India and South Africa, despite similar historical roots, developed divergent privilege regimes invented through constitutionally adopted philosophy.

INTRODUCTION

It was the Bill of Rights Act in 1689 in the United Kingdom, which authoritatively introduced democratic principles to the world and appears to be a vital source for the system of parliamentary privileges [1]. The purpose of "parliamentary privileges" is just that, where legislatures claim special legal jackets like privileges and immunities. The core and pious object of parliamentary privileges is to ensure that the free domain consists of valuable and coextensive rights and immunities to exercise legislative functions for the public good[2]. There exist two theologies in the world on the accountabilities of parliamentary privileges: non-accountability and inviolability. Britain, Canada, South Africa, and India rest upon the non-accountability principle, where legislatures are amenable to protection within the related scope of privileges, and protection cannot extend outside the scope of privileges. Whereas in France, the same is based on non-accountability as well as the inviolability principle, meaning legislatures are untouchable while maintaining parliamentary privileges[3].

On thorough scrutiny, it is seen that although India and South Africa have adopted the non-accountability principle for practical enforcement of parliamentary privileges, it principally depends on the existence of a complementary statute on powers, privileges and immunities in South Africa[4]. Further, the Indian constitution contains powers, privileges, and immunities under Articles 105 and 194 as transitional constitutional provisions without any supplementary legislation; hence, constitutional encounters are prone [5]. However, the parliamentary privilege mechanism introduced by the Republic of South Africa includes core constitutional provisions contained in Sections 58, 71, 11, and 161, supplemented by statutory enactments that appear more democratic and freer from encumbrances. Thus, this research paper aims to survey the complete philosophical and jurisprudential structure, including the historical foundation and functioning, that existed within both the Republics.

Meaning and Nature : The term "Parliamentary Privileges" is used as a synonym of the term "Parliamentary Immunity." Since both the democracies have conferred privileges upon "Parliament," "State," or "Province Legislatures," and in the case of South Africa, even to Municipal Councils, the phrase "Legislative Privileges" would be more suitable to define "Parliamentary Privileges" in the Indian as well as the South African domain [6]. Further, the

privileges or immunities are nothing but a constructive overview of the protection and guarantee to which a Parliament and its members are entitled for performing their duty for the public good[7]. Thus, privileges are like a right in rem to be enforced either by an individual member or an institution of parliament and consist of seeking protection or action of contempt in case of their breach.

Disparities and Dichotomy between Two Democracies: Though both democracies espoused the British Westminster privilege system in their constitution but implemented diverse mechanisms. In South Africa, after the Constitution of 1996, it has adopted more democratic inclusivity by introducing a three-tier privilege mechanism, viz., Parliament (Sections 58 and 71), Provincial Legislatures (Section 117) and Municipal Councils (Section 161)[8]. Additionally, the Parliament has enacted countrywide legislation, namely, the Powers, Privileges and Immunities of Parliament and Provincial Legislatures Act. 2004[9]. This exhaustive and national legislation laying down the scope and ambit for the utility of privileges is in supplement and addition to existing core constitutional provisions. This cemented a clear and unambiguous system resisting the British Westminster system and also giving less room for judicial intervention.

In India, we have a two-tier parliamentary system wherein the Parliament, under Article 105 and the State Legislatures, under Article 194, along with their members, have been bestowed with privileges and immunities by the Constitution[10]. Except for these transitional and core constitutional provisions, there is no statutory recognition of privileges and immunities, and therefore, as a convention, tradition, and practice, either we bank on Common Law privileges and precedents as existed till 1950, or we rest upon the courts seeking judicial review[11]. Thus, both democracies, being fundamentally diverse, are in consensus to maintain constitutional supremacy rather than Parliamentary exclusivity as existed in their common source. But on actual implementation of the privilege policy, there is disparity and dichotomy on account of the diverse modes so chosen[12].

Indian Framework: The Indian Constitution recognises discrete and official privileges as rights in rem to the members of the Parliament and State Legislatures and to those of the Parliament and State Assemblies. These immunities and privileges can also be invoked by using contempt jurisdiction, like the courts. Therefore, looking at constitutional provisions, farmers have adopted the two-tier privilege mechanism provided in Articles 105 and 194, where Parliament as well as State Legislatures are bestowed with privileges. Except for these core provisions, farmers were obstinate to enact any explanatory provisions in haste at the new beginning of the republic and hence left the scope of legislation to be decided at a later point

in time, which can be seen from Articles 105 (3) and 194 (3) [13]. However, it is an apathy amongst parliamentarians and legislators in India that constrained the Parliament to adopt British conventions and traditions rather than to enact nationwide legislation as contemplated under Articles 105 and 194 of the Constitution. Which indicates imperial domination and the vulnerability of the Parliament to deal with very basic parts of the Constitution, impacting the democratic well-being of the nation. This has led to a lot of confusion as to what the rights, responsibilities, and limits of the legislatures in India and of the Parliament and the State Assemblies[14].

Further, the mandate of Articles 122 and 212 creates implied restrictions upon the courts in India to deal with the functioning and working of the parliamentary regime on the touchstone of the principle of separation of powers adopted under the constitution. However, this restriction proved to be a fetter upon the natural rights of the citizens of India during the conflict of legislative privileges to that of basic rights enumerated in part three of the Constitution of India[15]. In India, the courts, being the third pillar of democracy as reflected under the Constitution, have proven their competence and role of guardian through various precedents, right from the Search Light case (1958)[16], the Presidential Reference case (1964)[17], Raja Ram Pal (2007)[18] and Sita Soren (2024)[19]. In summary, the parliamentary regime in India is restricted to the two-tier system affected by clouds of non-legislation, inviting unwarranted judicial intervention and also jeopardising fundamental guarantees of both legislatures as well as the citizens.

Nature of Privileges: In India, collectively, the privileges allow proceedings to be regulated, debates to be published, contempt to be punishable, and anything and everything said in parliament is safe from judicial scrutiny, and there is no fear of arrest. An individual member is bestowed with freedom of speech, exemption from arrest in civil cases during sessions, non-compulsory court testimony and control of internal procedures. This demonstrates that in India, the Parliament has adopted the non-accountability principle of protection in the functioning of parliamentary privileges and, recently, with judicial intervention, discarded the principle of inviolability protection in the exercise of privileges, immunities, and powers [20].

Since privileges, immunities, and powers are not limited to a member of the Parliament but extend to a member of State Legislatures, in India, the term “Legislative Privileges” is used in place of “parliamentary privileges,” which is squarely suited considering the targeted group mentioned in Articles 105 and 194 of the Constitution. Further, constitutional provisions encompassed in Articles 105 and 194 establish the position of legislative privileges as

transitional, as it provided for the framing of legislation, which was tried by the Parliament in 1977 [21].

Land Without Regulations: In India, the concept of privileges existed during the ancient period, which can be evidenced by the ancient systems of deliberation [22]. However, some milestones, such as the East India Company Acts, the Government of India Acts (1915, 1919, and 1935), and the Indian Independence Act of 1947, have gradually delineated awareness about the privileges and autonomy of the legislatures in India. But the system operates according to "the way things have always been done," and as a result, there is not a single, current statute that lays out the guidelines manifesting the working of parliamentary privileges. Today's privileges are enshrined in Articles 105 and 194 of the Indian Constitution, which give members of Parliament and State Legislators "freedom of speech in Parliament" and "State Legislature" and protect them from judicial prosecution for statements or votes made in the legislative context. Yet, what exactly falls under these privileges, how they intersect with citizens' rights, and how they are enforced remain subject to interpretation, tradition, and legal dispute[23].

Function of the Courts: The Indian framework relies on Articles 105 and 194 of the Constitution along with inherited British conventions and remains uncodified, often leading to situations where the courts abstain from intervention, leaving the ultimate authority to Parliament on arguing that Parliament should manage its own affairs, which can be manifested from judicial precedents like Pandit M. S. M. Sharma v. Shri Sri Krishna Sinha and Others and Keshav Singh v. Speaker, Legislative Assembly, Uttar Pradesh. The source of this silence is found in Article 122, which mandates the principle of separation. This implies that if the uncodified authority under Articles 105 and 194 is misused, a vacuum of mechanism is introduced by the Parliament. To put it simply, India's system may seem to be a strong instrument, but it sometimes makes it more difficult for the general public to hold individuals responsible, and the entry of the courts as protectors of the constitution provokes the relationship between the judiciary and legislatures. However, to date, Indian courts have balanced their responsibility successfully based on harmonious interpretation, upholding the superiority of the constitution [24].

Regime without Codification: According to clause (3) of Articles 105 and 194, the nature of protection to the institution as well as members would be equal to that of the British House of Commons on the day of India's independence, unless Parliament declared otherwise. So, these provisions ensure the residual power of Parliament as being the highest body in the matter of the regime of privileges, including codification [25]. Further, traits for codification can be

ascertained from the constitutional debates canvassed during the insertion of Articles 105 and 194 in the final text of the Constitution [26]. In addition to this, the Indian Parliament on several occasions asserted a need to codify its privileges into a clear statute; this can be demonstrated from perusal of parliamentary debates, but remains uncodified[30]. Also, an attempt to expunge common law overflow upon the parliamentary privileges regime in India can be recapitulated from the reading of section 21 of the Constitution (forty-second) Amendment Act, 1976 by which original clause (3) in Articles 105 and 194 was substituted but could not yield out of political vengeance and once again the legislature remains the only body with the power to choose its own privileges[27]. Thus, a well-defined legal framework in the arena of parliamentary privileges remains an unsolved democratic issue in India, which led to a lot of confusion since the Commons' rights are still based on previous decisions and are not formalised.

The main problem with this approach is how it handles free speech in the recent era of digital freedom. Although it is not expressly covered by other fundamental rights like the right to equality (Article 14) or the right to life and personal liberty (Article 21), free speech inside Parliament is protected under Article 105(1). This has led to situations where members may say hurtful or false things in the House without fear of repercussions, leaving those whose reputations or dignity have been harmed with no way to repair the damage [28]. The privilege becomes a weapon for the member rather than a protection for the organisation. The broad power to punish someone for "breach of privilege" is often used against journalists, activists and whistle-blowers who disparage members or inaccurately portray events. By suppressing free speech and public scrutiny of the legislature, this undermines the democratic idea of accountability [29].

South African Framework: Before the radical Constitution of 1996, parliamentary privileges in South Africa were primarily governed by the Powers and Privileges Act, 1963 [30]. Under the apartheid-era regime, the system operated through a three-layer parliamentary structure comprising the Parliament, Provinces, and Municipal Councils, which guaranteed freedom of speech and "exclusive cognisance" to their members.

The transition to a "post-liberation" democracy necessitated a shift in how these powers were controlled. The Parliament enacted the Powers, Privileges and Immunities of Parliament and Provincial Legislatures Act, 2004 [31], which fundamentally impacted the use and protection of privileges across all levels of government. In 2019, an amendment to this Act further refined the system by providing modern norms for managing disturbances and clearly defining the scope of the Speaker's powers [32]. Thus, South Africa's 1996 Constitution

provides a progressive source where the concept of "Constitutional Supremacy" dictates that any action that contravenes the Constitution is null and void [33]. While Section 58(1) grants members the right to free expression, Section 58(2) ensures this freedom is contingent upon the "rules and orders of the Assembly", striking a balance between constitutional ascendancy and parliament seclusion [34].

The constitutional fortification concerning privileges is available to all three stakeholders, namely the National Assembly, the National Council of Provinces, the Provincial Legislatures and the Municipal Councils and their members [35]. Additionally, the Parliament enacted the Powers, Privileges and Immunities of Parliament and Provincial Legislatures Act, 2004, impacting the use, protection and control of privileges by the members of the National Assembly, National Council of Provinces, Provincial Legislatures and Municipal Councils [40]. Toward its further pathfinder for deliberative and strong democracy, in 2019 the Parliament of South Africa brought an amendment to the Powers, Privileges and Immunities of parliament and Provincial Legislatures Act, 2004; thereby providing norms in cases of disturbances, contempt action for breach of privileges, and the arena of the Speaker's powers. Travelling through is more vital than privilege. South Africa's 1996 "post-liberation" Constitution provides a fundamentally different and more progressive basis. Section 58 of the South African Constitution discusses the National Assembly's authority. It maintains that the Constitution is the ultimate law and that these rights are clearly delineated. Above all, it is clear that the Constitution comes first. According to Section 2, the foundation of the whole system is the idea of Constitutional Supremacy, which maintains that the Constitution is the ultimate law and that any action that contravenes it is null and invalid. Members have the right to free expression under Section 58 (1); however, this freedom is quickly curtailed by Section 58(2), which claims that these rights are contingent on "the rules and orders of the Assembly [36].

The scope of privilege also includes freedom from arrest in civil matters during parliamentary sittings, as well as the power of the legislature to control its own processes. These are coupled with specific statutory guidelines via the Powers, Privileges and Immunities of Parliament and Provincial Legislatures Act [37]. Interpretation of statutes and balancing the authority of judicial precedent(s) in the context of parliamentary privileges is what the courts of both South Africa and India have tried ever since their Independence. Both jurisdictions start with the statutory interpretation of the law and end up being moulded by the influence of landmark case law [38].

Whenever statutory language conflicts with constitutional values and/or rights, the courts have always asserted the supremacy of the Constitution. This has always been the purpose behind

privileges being guided by the principles of legislative intent and a keen reading of the constitutional and statutory provisions. Judicial doctrine is balanced by legislative autonomy, wherein case laws are frequently cited to support constitutional interpretation(s). Indian courts have always kept space for modern reinterpretation of evolving democratic standards, keeping in mind public interest while following established precedents by interpreting statutory and constitutional provisions on parliamentary privileges.

Complete Constitutional Mandate: The South African system is comparable to a contemporary contract with well-defined guidelines. But India's approach resembles an ancient, custom-based handshake agreement impacting the natural rights of its citizens. In South Africa, privilege is interpreted solely as a tool to enable the "effective performance of functions" rather than a shield for parliamentary supremacy[39]. In South Africa, the Constitution spells out regulations manifesting the working of parliamentary privileges in detail. Under the Constitution, what a member of parliament may do is clearly outlined. Their right to free expression is subject to the rights of all people; however, the courts have the authority to intervene and prevent Parliament from abusing its authority, such as by suspending a member without cause[40].

Role of the Courts: In South Africa, the courts act as impartial referees. The judiciary has the explicit authority to ensure that parliamentary powers do not infringe upon the Bill of Rights. This includes the power to review and invalidate legislative actions, as evidenced in the judicial pronouncements such as *Poovalingam* (1992), *De Lille* (1998), *Dikoko* (2006), *Democratic Alliance* (2015), *Swartboo* (2021), and *Economic Freedom Fighters* (2024), where courts have played a pivotal role in establishing the privilege regime and balancing exclusive cognizance of the legislative domain [41]. The courts have the authority to review and invalidate legislation made by Parliament to safeguard people's rights. In cases of bribery and contempt, while referring to judicial precedents and constitutional bench judgements as authoritative guides, the Supreme Court uses its discretion to limit privileges [42]. All things considered, Parliament has a great deal of unchecked authority. Parliament's authority and the people's rights are equal. Both nations see parliamentary privileges as important for legislative independence, but their different constitutional histories show that they have adopted different ways of balancing autonomy with accountability. This comparison shows that South Africa relies on clear constitutional codification, while India combines constitutional provisions with inherited conventions, leading to different problems and changes[44].

Judicial Review: South Africa and India both see parliamentary privileges as essential tools for legislative independence, but their different constitutional histories, legal definitions, and

levels of judicial involvement show that they have adopted different ways of balancing parliamentary autonomy with democratic accountability. Under the apartheid Constitution, the power of judicial review of legislative deeds in South Africa is expressly embodied under section 172. unlikely in India, where the power of judicial review came to be established by virtue of constitutional interpretation. The system in South Africa is comparable to a contemporary contract with well-defined guidelines and an impartial arbiter (the courts) to ensure equity. However, India's approach is similar to an ancient, custom-based handshake agreement that sometimes seems to be biased in favour of the wealthy and mighty.

This contrast confirms that South Africa relies on clear constitutional codification in the matter of judicial review, while the Indian constitution combines constitutional provisions with common law inherited doctrine, which proves difficult for the courts to deal with the parliamentary privilege regime.

CONCLUSION

Comparing parliamentary privileges in South Africa and India shows that, despite a shared British heritage, the concept has developed in very different ways. India continues to rely on a mix of constitutional text, inherited customs, and changing judicial rulings. Articles 105 and 194 support lively debate within the legislature, but the absence of statutory codification has led to a situation where privilege is sometimes pushed beyond its intended limits. Unclear definitions, discretionary applications, and limited judicial review have led to instances where privileges shield lawmakers from public accountability instead of enriching democratic discussion. Thus, India's reliance on uncodified customs has occasionally blurred the distinction between rightful legislative protection and the abuse of power.

On the contrary South Africa's system offers a different model which clearly defines the nature and reach of parliamentary privileges and integrates them into a broader rights-based framework by virtue of the 2004 and 2019 enactments. Judicial oversight ensures that these privileges do not override fundamental constitutional rights. Courts routinely step in when legislative actions clash with constitutional values, asserting that privilege is not a means of unchecked power but a necessary component of effective governance. This clarity minimizes the risk of misuse and reinforces the balance between parliamentary independence and citizens' rights.

The comparison reveals that, while both countries value strong and independent legislatures, India's uncodified approach allows for greater uncertainty. Moving toward a clearer statutory framework without compromising the essential freedom of speech in Parliament would help India align privileges with constitutional principles and democratic accountability. Ultimately,

parliamentary privileges should protect institutional integrity rather than shield representatives from responsibility to the people they represent.

Suggestion: Both democracies, however, have strong and independent parliaments that operate in somewhat distinct ways. To strengthen its democracy, India should consider adopting the South African model and enacting a contemporary, unambiguous statutory regime that outlines these rights as discussed during making of the constitution. Such a regime would safeguard free expression without infringing on the rights of the populace, and this can be done within the supreme authority of the Constitution, as established in *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala*. Thus, for India to strengthen its democracy, it must move toward a clearer statutory framework for the legislative codification of Articles 105 and 194.

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